

Exploring new sources of information to study the influence of scientific research in policy documents

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Introduction

The open science movement has become especially relevant in recent years, modifying how scientific knowledge is produced and disseminated. In this new framework, the influence and impact of scientific activities on other non-academic audiences have been of increasing interest. Its analysis and assessment are challenging for studies on the evaluation and impact of scientific activity. In this sense, bibliometrics' traditional toolbox has been expanded by adding altmetric indicators (Priem & Hemminger, 2010) to analyse scientific production's impact on non-scientific audiences. So, to bolster how social impact is evaluated (beyond simply counting up mentions on social networks), it might be interesting to look at new information sources that collect the documents with potential impact on society. One example studied in recent years is policy documents. Studies propose that the relationship between science and government publications may be a good indicator of how science influences the institutions that have decision-making power or influence society. Several research areas have endeavoured to analyse how scientific knowledge flows from academia to policy documents (Bornmann et al., 2016; Newson et al., 2018; Pinheiro et al., 2021; Yin et al., 2022).

Analyses like these have traditionally been done by applying text-mining techniques to policy documents. The creation of the Altmetric.com tool was the first step toward the construction of databases of policy documents. Later, in 2019 Overton (overton.io) arose, a database that in 2021 had over 30,000 policy documents from governments, think tanks, governmental organisations, and ONGDs (Szomszor & Adie, 2022). To test the scope of these sources, we have recently analysed the impact of scientific papers on open science, signed by centres in Spain, in policy documents using Overton (Sastrón-Toledo & De Filippo, 2022). To complement the study, we have proposed to explore other sources of information with potential value in the field of public policy to

assess their possible use to measure the influence of scientific texts in policy documents.

Source and Methodology

The source of information used was the Catalogue of Publications of the General State Administration of Spain (CPAGE, <https://cpage.mpr.gob.es>). This digital platform gathers the publications published by Spanish Ministries and Public Bodies since 2001 and includes monographs, scientific journals, draft law reports and cartographies.

For its analysis, an initial content test was carried out to assess the most relevant documents for analysis. Academic publications (books and scientific journals) have been removed from the study since they are produced by academic authors, therefore their primary references are also from the academic world. We have chosen to analyse two specific types of documents. Firstly "draft law reports", documents prepared by technical bodies of the different Ministries which analyse the impact of different draft laws. Secondly "government strategies," which include the public governance roadmap and objectives to be promoted and implemented by the government. All the documents of both types were downloaded, and an in-depth study of the "draft law reports" has been started. Content cleaning has been carried out to eliminate duplicates.

To obtain systematised and comparable information, a series of criteria were defined, both structural and content-related: i) document identifier; ii) title; iii) institutional author; iv) structure of the text; v) references cited (identifying the type of document cited: monograph, scientific journal, technical report, bill, legal information, and the type of authorship: international organisations, public body, academic institutions, ONGs, private sector); and vi) type of citation (the description of the procedure followed for citation).

Preliminary Results

Eighteen project reports and 256 government strategies were identified. Their main characteristics are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: Structure and content of the documents

Indicator	Result
Documental type	Draft law reports, government strategies
Date of publication	2012-2022
Author	Ministry (Equality; Social Rights and Agenda 2030; Presidency; Health; Justice)
Structure	Technical documents with tables and figures, standardised structure
Topic	Impact of issues related to: Gender; Childhood, adolescence and family; SDGs, in the General State Budget Law.

Regarding citations to other texts, draft law reports usually mention other official documents from the Ministries and Public Bodies: laws, royal decrees, regulations, strategic plans, the Official State Gazette, etc. In general, they reference the National Institute of Statistics and national surveys (of the Ministry of Health or Consumer Affairs) as the source of information presented in tables and graphs. In a few cases, reports from international organisations such as UNESCO, OECD, United Nations, World Trade Organization, and Eurostat are mentioned. There are few mentions of scientific articles (<1% of the references), reports from academic centres. Bibliographic references are not cited in a standardised way (there are no bibliographic lists. Only the title of the reports is mentioned in the text, or the web page -as a footnote-containing the cited information is included.

Conclusions

The creation of the CPAGE allows access to a significant number of official documents that can be consulted freely and free of charge, which is part of the transparency and accessibility strategy of the Spanish public administration. The purpose of using this tool was to check whether the texts produced by the Spanish Administration have used scientific-academic documents (as a source of information, theoretical framework or methodological reference). Preliminary analysis shows that, in policy documents, reference to scientific-academic material is scarce and the use of information produced by the public administration predominates. The external sources used and consulted have been reports from international organisations, generally surveys or reports with statistical data. There is no use of methodological or conceptual material from the

academic sector, which may limit the studies to an exclusively technical-professional sphere without considering the advances in the scientific literature. This analysis shows that, in the case of the documents analysed, the relationship between the academia and the public policy sphere is scarce since there is no feedback in terms of content. A detailed study of other policy documents will allow us to determine whether other texts incorporate academic advances or whether this disconnection is frequent in all cases. It will also allow us to assess whether using the Administration's sources is relevant for this type of research.

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